

Résumé for Researchers-like Narrative CV: Template Synthesis

Purpose

This [Résumé for Researchers](#) (R4R)-like narrative CV template synthesis aims to provide a summary of the ways in which R4R-like narrative CV templates are being used by some of the members of the [Joint Funders Group](#) in January 2022.

Table 1: Summary of findings

Across a sample of 10 funders in January 2022 the following was observed:

CV template contains a section aligned to R4R section header								
Funder	Personal details	Module 1: How have you contributed to the generation of knowledge?	Module 2: How have you contributed to the development of individuals?	Module 3: How have you contributed to the wider research community?	Module 4: How have you contributed to broader society?	Personal statement	Additions	ORCID iD
1	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No
2	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No
3	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	No	Yes	Yes
4	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
5	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
6	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No
7	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
8	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	Yes
9	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	No	Yes	Yes
10	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	Yes

Synthesis of findings

Extent of use

- Most (6/10) of the narrative CVs have been or are currently being used (including use within pilots) in at least one of the funders opportunities. 4/10 are planned to be piloted from 2022.
- All funders require Principal Investigator (lead applicant) to complete the R4R-Like CV, most (6/10) also require the R4R-Like CV to be completed by the Co-Principal Investigator (co-applicant/co-leads); not all funding opportunities using the R4R-like CV allow for Co-Principal Investigators (co-applicants/co-leads). One funder additionally requires R4R-Like CV completion by collaborators and mentors and one funder intends to require completion by all named staff.

Template headers/sections

- All funders ask applicants for personal details; however most (6/10) do not include this specific ask within the CV template as these details are collected elsewhere within the application process.
- All funders are using the question headings/sections for modules 1, 2 and 3 from the Royal Society R4R template using the same or similar wording.
- 8/10 funders are also employing the module 4 question with the same or similar wording. One of these funders combines modules 1 and 4 in a single header. Another funder combines module 3

and 4 in single header. One funder identified perceived challenges with the guidance for reviewers for Module 4 being a deterrent factor in its current use.

- All funders include 'Additions'. Four of these CV templates have the section titled 'Career Breaks' rather than 'Additions'. One indicated within supplementary guidance that this information could be included within the Personal Details section. One funder includes the 'Additions' section in a separate part of the application form from the R4R-like CV.
- Although not a header/section within the R4R CV template, the majority (7/10) provide space within the application for applicants to include their [ORCID iD](#) (a persistent digital identifier), with 2 funders providing an explicit location for the ORCID iD within the CV template.

Word/Page Length of CVs

- The length of the CV and sections varied across the R4R-like CV templates, with some (4/10) CVs highlighting word count limits per sections and a few (3/10) indicating a page length limit. The lengths/limits of the remaining (3/10) are not yet determined as they are yet to be piloted.
 - Of those (4/10) providing word limits:
 - one provided a total word limit across the four modules of 1,000 words, with no word limit on the personal statement,
 - two provided word limits which varied by Module; however, both allocated a higher word limit to Module 1 (500 or 300 words) compared to the other modules (which varied from 300 to 200 words).
 - one funder plans for a consistent word limit of 250 words per section.
 - no funders indicated minimum word requirements.
 - Of those (3/10) providing page limits:
 - this varied from a maximum of 2 pages to a maximum of 5 pages
 - one funder provides a varying page limit depending on the role of the individual completing the R4R-Like CV (Lead Applicant and Co-Applicant or Collaborator and Mentor).
 - no funders indicated minimum page requirements.
- Some funders noted consideration of reviewer capacity and grant system set-ups/limitations being a determining factor in the decision of setting word vs page limits.

Common features

- An illustrative example showing the common features of the CV template can be found in the Annotated R4R CV template (see [Résumé Library](#)).

Next Steps

- There is an aspiration to revisit the CV template synthesis with updated information in light of reviews and evaluations.

Version Control

<u>Version Number</u>	<u>Status</u>	<u>Revision Date</u>	<u>Author(s)</u>	<u>Summary of Changes</u>
1.0	Complete	March 2022	Joint Funders Group	New resource created